

The Gen-Ba Knowledge Sharing Workshop Support System Using Large Language Models: Experimental Evaluation in a Plant Cultivation Workshop

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Abstract

This paper presents a study on the knowledge management of on-site knowledge, referred to as "Gen-Ba Knowledge", which is found in fields such as agriculture, nursing care, and maintenance inspection. Gen-Ba knowledge often includes tacit and latent elements that are highly context-dependent and difficult to formalize into manuals. As such, sharing this type of knowledge has been a persistent challenge, and effective knowledge management practices have not been fully established. To address this, we developed a method that utilizes a Smart Voice Messaging System (SVMS) to capture Gen-Ba knowledge in real time through voice input from workers, which is then shared among organizational members through knowledge-sharing workshops. We have applied this method in various field settings and confirmed its effectiveness in facilitating the transfer of Gen-Ba knowledge. However, in previous implementations, the tasks of organizing collected knowledge for workshops and facilitating productive discussions imposed a considerable burden on team members—especially facilitators—thus posing a significant obstacle to the sustainable adoption of the method. In this paper, we propose a novel approach to address these challenges by leveraging a Large Language Models (LLMs). Specifically, we introduce a mechanism that supports effective knowledge sharing by suggesting contextually relevant messages to stimulate deeper discussion during workshops. We applied the proposed method to the domain of plant cultivation, confirming its effectiveness in enhancing the sharing of Gen-Ba knowledge. By incorporating state-of-the-art AI technologies into the management of latent knowledge—traditionally difficult to handle—this research demonstrates a novel contribution to the field of knowledge management.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Japan's declining birthrate and aging population have created a need to increase labor productivity per worker, with AI (Artificial Intelligence) being utilized across various fields as an effective means to improve efficiency. However, Frey and Osborne [1] noted that tasks heavily reliant on workers' perceptions and sensory judgment, where it is necessary to think and act flexibly in response to environmental changes, are unlikely to be replaced by AI.

On-site work requires flexible response adapted to surrounding context to address unexpected situations not documented in manuals. However, responses based on understanding the on-site situation depend on the site-specific context. Such knowledge (Gen-Ba Knowledge), while not explicitly documented but potentially verbalizable according to the situation, is difficult to manage. Consequently, it is easily forgotten and difficult to utilize away from the original context. Traditionally, such knowledge has been transmitted between workers sharing the same workspace through on-the-job training. However, in Japan's current situation, where productivity demands remain high despite decreasing workforce numbers, and in fields where workers are geographically dispersed (such as agriculture and customer maintenance), sharing valuable experiential knowledge is crucial for effective practice. Nevertheless, efforts to share Gen-Ba knowledge across different sites remain challenging, with learning of tacit knowledge largely dependent on individual workers' initiative. Therefore, it is very important to support Gen-Ba knowledge sharing efforts.

In the field of AI, Large Language Models (LLMs) have evolved significantly since the introduction of the transformer architecture [2], facilitating easier processing of unstructured data and enabling broader data utilization. For example, LLMs can organize information and enable rapid access, helping workers acquire necessary knowledge efficiently. We consider LLMs a viable technology for sharing latent knowledge without burdening on-site operations. The knowledge sharing support method proposed in this paper facilitates Gen-Ba knowledge sharing in workshops conducted away from the site by facilitating discussions through LLM utilization.

This paper is composed as follows. Existing research on efforts to share field knowledge is introduced and the issues addressed in this study are outlined. Then, previous studies are reviewed and research gaps are identified. We present

Figure 1. Continuous Gen-Ba Knowledge Layers. Adapted from [5].

a proposed approach to solving the problem and evaluate the proposed approach through experimental testing. The evaluation results are presented, followed by a discussion and conclusions.

GEN-BA KNOWLEDGE

Gen-Ba refers to the environment in which humans work. The term consists of two words: “Gen” meaning real and actual, and “Ba” referring to the knowledge-creating space as proposed by Nonaka and Konno [3]. Uchihira et al. [4] define Gen-Ba knowledge as the knowledge that humans perceive, feel, and think about objects in their working environment. Gen-Ba knowledge is latent knowledge that depends on context and exists between explicit knowledge and tacit knowledge (Figure 1). Consequently, it is difficult to formalize like If-Then rules and tends to remain internalized within on-site workers. This study adopts the definition established by Uchihira et al. [4, 5].

How to Share Gen-Ba Knowledge

In contrast to the Digital Twin, which utilizes only data that can be collected by sensors, Uchihira et al. [4] propose the Digital Knowledge Twin. Digital Knowledge Twin includes Gen-Ba knowledge such as human senses and experiences that cannot be captured by sensors. The Digital Knowledge Twin consists of “Knowledge Collection”, “Systematization”, and “Utilization”.

“Knowledge Collection” can be achieved using Uchihira’s Smart Voice Message System (SVMS) [6]. SVMS records fragment of Gen-Ba knowledge of what workers do, feel, and think in the field, as voice and photographs. This enables the capture of Gen-Ba knowledge before it is lost, even during on-site work when it is difficult to operate digital devices. We define “awareness messages” as textual or image recordings of the collected Gen-Ba knowledge.

Inoue and Uchihira [7] propose the knowledge sharing workshop method in which awareness messages collected by SVMS are manually organized and accumulated. Utilizing collected awareness messages as a catalyst, discussions enable the exchange of Gen-Ba knowledge, incorporating the site-specific context associated with the collected messages. This corresponds to “Knowledge Systematization” and “Utilization” phase in Digital Knowledge Twin. On the other hand, the systematization and utilization phase of the existing Gen-Ba knowledge sharing method has the following issues: “Man-Hours for Preparation” and “Dependence on Facilitator Capability”.

1. Man-Hours for Preparation

As the number of awareness messages to be collected increases, the man-hours required to classify and organize the messages also increase. As a result, the preparation time for knowledge-sharing workshops becomes longer. This prevents smooth knowledge sharing. Ogawa et al. [8] proposed the method to solve this issue by using LLMs to classify the awareness messages, which is effective in reducing the man-hours required.

2. Dependence on Facilitator Capability

Workshops for sharing Gen-Ba knowledge require high-quality discussions to elicit workers' past experiences and Gen-Ba knowledge. A large proportion of these discussions depend on the facilitator. For example, the flow of problem-solving and decision-making is influenced by the facilitator's perception of important issues. The process of eliciting key issues from awareness messages also depends on the facilitator's understanding and perspective on the problems (Path Dependency). Therefore, useful awareness messages are missed and become an obstacle to knowledge sharing. This study mainly focuses on this issue.

RELATED RESEARCH

Knowledge management has been widely studied. However, there is criticism that many of these studies focus only on explicit knowledge [9]. They often do not address tacit knowledge, which exists in the human mind. There is also a criticism that knowledge management research only deals with the knowledge of symbolic workers and does not pay enough attention to the workers on the on-site workers who are actually running the production site [10].

In recent years, with the development of LLMs as represented by ChatGPT, conventional IT systems and database-based knowledge management systems have been handling unstructured data, such as natural language and photographs. In response to this, there are many studies that utilize Natural Language Processing (NLP) in knowledge management using digital technology [11]. However, most of these studies focus on explicit knowledge [5, 7]. However, it is difficult to apply digital technology to knowledge that cannot be explicitly externalized. In particular, it has been discussed that the use of NLP is not suitable for processing complex contexts contained in unstructured, incomplete texts with inconsistent vocabularies [12, 13].

Furthermore, the emergence of LLMs, which are pre-trained based on large corpora, has greatly improved the performance of inference processing. This advancement enables the processing of complex texts by supplementing missing context through inference. Therefore, LLMs can deal with complex texts relatively effectively, and the use of LLMs in knowledge management has been attempted in the form of integrating LLMs with knowledge management by taking advantage of LLM's reasoning [14]. LLMs has been used mainly for knowledge retrieval, but the target is still limited to knowledge that can be formally represented [15, 16].

As Orr [17] points out, situation-dependent knowledge acquired through trial and error in the Gen-Ba is shared in the form of storytelling. In other words, knowledge that is difficult to externalized formally is shared through dialogue, including context. Therefore, workshops in the form of dialogue are effective for sharing knowledge within an organization. LLMs has been actively used to support group work [18]. In addition, Imamura et al. [19] have pointed out the possibility of facilitating creative group work in collaboration between humans and LLMs. Thus, the use of LLMs has been studied with a focus on communication support. However, no matter how well LLMs develop, generic LLMs do not include "Gen-Ba Knowledge", which is field-specific knowledge. In addition, LLMs can produce knowledge that does not exist in LLMs, such as hallucination [20], which can lead to incorrect answers.

RAGs and their development and improvement are being addressed as a solution to these problems. On the other hand, existing RAG studies target already existing documents, which can be seen as an extension of existing document-based knowledge management systems. Therefore, they are not able to respond to the knowledge management of human knowledge and knowledge management targeting on-site workers that Nakano [10] criticize. In the future, a knowledge management method that continuously collects Gen-Ba Knowledge that is not included in general-purpose LLMs will be required to realize work support in a form that can be used by on-site workers while effectively utilizing LLMs.

From the above, it is important to support space for sharing knowledge that is difficult to externalize formally, such as Gen-Ba knowledge. However, since the utilization of LLMs has focused on knowledge that can be externalized formally, research integrating them is limited. Therefore, methods to support the sharing of latent knowledge remain an important issue in knowledge management research.

PROPOSAL METHOD

In this study, we propose a method of using LLM to support the facilitation of discussions that externalize Gen-Ba knowledge in order to realize a knowledge management method that supports the sharing of Gen-Ba knowledge in a workshop. The proposed method (Figure 2) consists of three steps. The first step is the collection of awareness messages by SVMS. The second step is a discussion based on these awareness messages of interest, in which participants

select the messages of interest to them and discuss them. The third step is a discussion based on the related awareness messages to selected awareness messages. The proposed method enables each participant to easily externalize their Gen-Ba knowledge, which used to be dependent on the facilitator, because related awareness messages are easy to refer to.

Figure 2. Proposed Method for Supporting Gen-Ba Knowledge Sharing Using LLM

Development of a Workshop Support System

We have developed a workshop support system that displays related awareness messages in a knowledge sharing workshop to facilitate discussions that externalize Gen-Ba knowledge (Figure 3).

The similarity search by cosine similarity using LLM is effective in extracting related awareness messages [21]. For LLM, we use the GLuCoSE¹, which is a model that has been shown to be effective in eliciting related awareness messages in [21]. Since this model was developed based on Luke [22], a language model was constructed using an entity-annotated corpus. Therefore, GLuCoSE can identify related terms without requiring domain-specific fine-tuning.

For the backend, we used LLM, which calculates the distance between awareness messages using cosine similarity, by calling its API in gradio [23]. The front-end framework is React², which can be used as a web tool to easily display related awareness messages (Figure 3). This support system is designed to support discussions by displaying awareness messages related to the discussions contained in the search results in the third step of the proposed method.

Figure 3. Workshop Support System Developed

¹ <https://huggingface.co/pkshatech/GLuCoSE-base-en>

² <https://react.dev/>

The following Figure 4 shows the implementation screen of the support system. All awareness messages collected with the images are displayed in relation to the worker who recorded them and the target task. When clicking on the target awareness message, contextually similar awareness messages are displayed in order of similarity using LLM (Figure 5). The third step of discussion is based on the results of this system’s search.

Figure 4. Screenshot of Workshop Support System Implementation (Before searching)

Figure 5. Screenshot of Workshop Support System Implementation (Searching)

EXPERIMENT OVERVIEW

The following sections provide a detailed overview of the experiments conducted to evaluate the proposed method. First, in the “SVMS trial”, implementing the Smart Voice Message System (SVMS) to collect Gen-Ba knowledge fragments as awareness messages during plant cultivation work. Subsequently, we conducted a workshop to discuss these collected awareness messages, facilitating the sharing of Gen-Ba knowledge that typically remains internalized within individual on-site workers.

In the “Knowledge Sharing Workshop”, a support system displayed awareness messages relevant to ongoing discussion. This helps evaluate the system’s effectiveness in externalizing Gen-Ba knowledge, which was previously dependent on the skills of the facilitators. After participants discussed their pre-selected awareness messages, additional time was allocated for further discussion based on the related messages presented by the support system. We evaluated our proposed method using workshop dialogue transcripts, participant questionnaires, and follow-up interviews. TABLE 1 summarizes the parameters of the evaluation experiment.

Table 1. Experiment Overview

Category	Description
Number of Participants	7 people (Participants A to G)
Target Work	Plant Cultivation
SVMS Trial Period	67 days
Collected Messages	440 messages
Workshop Time	2h

Collecting Awareness Messages with SVMS

In order to collect fragments of Gen-Ba knowledge of field workers, SVMS was trialed for plant cultivation, and awareness messages were collected. The target plant cultivation requires not only environmental factors such as temperature and sunlight, but also workers' judgment in such tasks as watering and fertilizing.

Figure 6 is an image of the plant cultivation collected during the SVMS trial. In addition, this trial involved cultivation at different sites for different workers in order to make the situation more similar to actual on-site work. Therefore, the situations encountered by the workers are similar actions. On the other hand, this is a trial in which site-dependent work occurs and work at other sites is not shared in real time.

Collecting awareness message was conducted in Japanese, and discussions were likewise.

Figure 6. Plants Grown as Part of the SVMS Trial Work

Knowledge Sharing Workshop

In the workshop, participants selected messages of interest from the collected awareness messages and had time to share their Gen-Ba knowledge through discussions based on the selected messages. After a discussion of the messages to be discussed, the support system displays the messages that are related to the selected messages. The workshop participants discuss the messages by referring to the related messages.

This was repeated for all the pre-selected awareness messages. In the conventional method, the selection of related awareness messages was an individual task, and although important messages could be elicited, only the pre-selected messages were utilized, and the selection was dependent on the facilitator's capability. The display of related awareness messages by the support system in the proposed method replaces the facilitator-dependent work. Conversation logs were collected by converting workshop conversations into text.

Example of a Knowledge-Sharing Workshop

The discussion was conducted in Japanese, and a translation of the discussion log text is shown in Figure 7. The discussion was based on the awareness messages selected in the preparation by the participants. The discussion based on selected awareness messages focused on airflow in cultivation. This discussion did not lead to a discussion on how to improve airflow. The discussion was then conducted by referring to the awareness messages displayed by

the support system. Using the messages of similar situations at other sites, a comprehensive discussion of similar situations was conducted. The discussion led to the conclusion that thinning work is important to improve airflow, and each worker's Gen-Ba knowledge was externalized through the discussion. Figure 8 is a diagram that organizes the utterances based on Figure 7.

Figure 7. Transcribed Workshop Log

Figure 8. Organized Workshop Log

EVALUATION METHOD AND RESULTS

A questionnaire was used to survey the workshop participants to evaluate the awareness messages displayed by the system and the knowledge externalized through the discussion. Afterwards, a 20-minute interview was conducted with each participant based on the responses to the questionnaire. The results of the questionnaire are shown in TABLE 2. Participant's were divided in their evaluation of whether the awareness messages displayed by the support system contained interesting messages. In the interviews, participants with low evaluations rated the displayed awareness messages as similar and thus did not get any new ideas.

In contrast, participants with high ratings rated the awareness messages as interesting because they included related and unexpected information about similar situations. In other words, in a knowledge sharing workshop, useful awareness messages that facilitate discussion need to include related contexts, yet be unexpected. It is important that participants be able to capture the context related to the discussion and the awareness message, for example, an awareness message from a similar but different site to the situation mentioned in the discussion.

On the other hand, the discussion using the support system made the participants feel that the quantity and quality of communication were both improved. This indicates that many of the participants felt that the use of related awareness messages was effective for the discussion. This was not because the awareness messages displayed by the search system shared Gen-Ba knowledge, but because they inspired the participant’s latent knowledge. This inspiration led to the externalization of related contexts through the discussion, effectively facilitating the conversation.

In summary, the awareness messages proposed by the support system were based on contextual similarity. However, some of them contained unexpectedness, and the latent context between the awareness messages was externalized, facilitating the discussion of shared Gen-Ba knowledge.

Table 2. Excerpt from the Questionnaire Results

Question	Description			
Q1	Did the search system show any other important messages besides the ones you chose to discuss?			
Scales	Disagree		Agree	
participants	3		4	
Q2	How effective did you feel the awareness messages indicated by the search system were for the discussion?			
Scales	Disagree	Slight Disagree	Slight Agree	Agree
Participants	0	1	2	4
Q3	Do you think the proposed method has improved the amount of communication?			
Scales	Disagree	Slight Disagree	Slight Agree	Agree
participants	0	0	3	4
Q4	Do you think the proposed method has improved the quality of communication?			
Scales	Disagree	Slight Disagree	Slight Agree	Agree
participants	0	0	4	3

DISCUSSION

The discussion expanded, taking into account the insights and messages as follows.

A. Comprehensive Discussion on Similar Situation

The proposed method revealed solutions to problems and situation-dependent Gen-Ba knowledge that could not be achieved through conventional methods. This was possible because discussions were based on awareness messages related to similar objects and situations. Our approach supports the externalization of Gen-Ba knowledge about similar situations in workshops. This knowledge is typically only accessible to those who directly experience the same work environment and is difficult to share in settings where workers are geographically dispersed.

Mori [24] explains that the process of forming working concepts occurs through the accumulation of multiple individual responses, enabling application across different sites. The discussion approach in our proposed method supports the formation of applicable working concepts by identifying awareness messages that likely contain similar individual responses through similarity search, thereby facilitating Gen-Ba knowledge sharing.

B. Path Dependence of the Facilitator

In evaluating awareness messages, path dependence means skilled facilitators can accurately identify messages relevant to issues other workers might encounter. However, their selection criteria depend heavily on personal experience and knowledge. The contextual similarities recognized by LLMs often differ from the relationships humans perceive between awareness messages. Our proposed method leverages these different perspectives in discussions, creating a collaborative approach between LLMs and humans for utilizing awareness messages. This multi-perspective approach is crucial for externalizing Gen-Ba knowledge effectively.

The proposed method overcomes the "What You Look For Is What You Find" phenomenon [25] by utilizing related awareness messages to enhance and enrich discussions beyond the facilitator’s initial focus.

C. Support for the Externalization of Gen-Ba Knowledge

In discussions based on selected awareness messages of interest, individual messages trigger the externalization of Gen-Ba knowledge, including site-specific context. However, the context that can emerge in such discussions is limited by the facilitator's expertise.

In contrast, discussions based on related awareness messages identified through LLM-powered similarity search use these messages as anchors to capture and explore surrounding contextual information, helping externalize latent on-site context that facilitates deeper discussion (Figure 9). This approach can evoke Gen-Ba knowledge from various work environments, thereby reducing dependence on facilitator expertise in knowledge-sharing workshops.

Figure 9. Conceptual Model of Knowledge Externalization on the Ground through Similar Awareness Messages

CONCLUSION

The proposed method in this paper collects awareness messages from the site and uses a workshop support system utilizing LLM to appropriately suggest similar messages.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed method, a laboratory experiment was conducted in which participants grew basil in different sites. A trial was then conducted in which the cultivation knowledge of the workers was shared in a workshop. This is a method to support the sharing of Gen-Ba knowledge, which is targeted at sites where workers are dispersed, and the use of LLM supports the externalization of latent Gen-Ba knowledge by the workers. This is a knowledge management method using LLM for Gen-Ba knowledge that has not been formally externalized.

This paper demonstrates the effectiveness of LLM utilization through end-to-end trials, from the collection of awareness messages to the implementation and evaluation of a practical knowledge sharing workshop support system. However, the evaluation in this study was an experimental quality experiment conducted with a small number of evaluators, and an evaluation with a larger number of participants is needed to generalize the obtained effectiveness.

The proposed method shows how Gen-Ba knowledge can be represented through search functions and workshop discussions. Furthermore, the proposed method is effective for improving the quality of discussions, which used to depend on the facilitator. It also serves as an important basis for establishing Gen-Ba knowledge-sharing initiatives in organizations with distributed on-site work. Furthermore, the integration of generative models such as GPT [26] with search functions represents a promising avenue for future research. In addition to the awareness message, a structured description of the externalized description in the workshop allows the LLM to be used with less hallucination.

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